

A REVIEW ON BIOLOGICAL ACTIVITIES OF ISATIN DERIVATIVES

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ABSTRACT:

Isatin is a nitrogen containing heterocyclic compound found abundantly in nature. Isatin derivatives gained importance recently due to potent pharmacological and biological effect of the ring. Isatin and its derivatives possess various biological activities like antitumor, antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, antiviral, anticonvulsant, antioxidant, analgesic and CNS depressant. The present review outlines the use of isatin derivatives for its biological and pharmacological properties

KEYWORDS : Isatin, Heterocyclic Compound, Tribulin, Biological activity

1. INTRODUCTION

Isatin is an important class of nitrogen containing heterocyclic aromatic compounds found in plants, human blood and tissue and acts as important species for the synthesis of various heterocyclic compounds especially, indolic and quinolinic compounds. Tribulin was the initial name given to isatin. Erdman and Laurent developed isatin by oxidizing indigo dye with chromic acid and nitric acid. Isatin undergoes various chemical reactions such as oxidation, N acylation, Friedal Crafts reaction, N Halogenation etc. Isatin derivatives show a broad spectrum of biological activities such as antibacterial, antifungal, antiviral, anti-inflammatory, anti-convulsant and anticancer drug. Semaxanib, Orantinib, Sunitinib and Nintedanib are isatin based drugs that have been in clinical use.

indoline-2,3-dione

PHYSICAL PROPERTIES

- ✓ Color: orange solid
- ✓ Molecular weight: 147.13g/mol
- ✓ Melting point: 202 – 203 °C
- ✓ Solubility: soluble in polar organic solvents (methanol, acetone, acetonitrile)
- ✓ Partially soluble in CHCl_3 , CH_2Cl_2
- ✓ Insoluble in non polar organic solvents like hexane, toluene and benzene

2. BIOLOGICAL ACTIVITIES OF ISATIN DERIVATIVES

A. ANTICANCER ACTIVITY

- Amna Qasem Ali *et.al* in 2014 reported the synthesis of isatin thiosemicarbazones and studied their *in vitro* anti cancer activity. The new Schiff bases were evaluated for their DNA binding, cleavage and *in vitro* anti proliferative activities in human colon cancer cell line. The results of gel electrophoresis indicate that these Schiff bases induced cleavage of plasmid DNA.

- Sachin Laxman Munde *et.al* in 2021 reported the synthesis and evaluation of cytotoxic activity of isatin derivatives. *In vitro* cytotoxic effect of the synthesized derivatives was evaluated on the growth of allium cepa root meristem and the effect was compared with standard cytotoxic drug cyclophosphamide.

- S. Shobha Rani *et.al* in 2010 synthesized, characterized and studied the *in vitro* cytotoxic activity of N – alkyl derivatives of isatin. The new series of isatin and triazole derivatives was characterized by spectral data and screened for *in vitro* cytotoxic activities like MTT assay, Tryphan blue dye exclusion method, antimetabolic activity against colon and lung cancer cell lines.

- Chengyuan Liang *et.al* in 2014 studied the *in vitro* and *in vivo* antitumor activity of symmetrical bis Schiff base derivative of isatin by condensation of the natural or synthetic isatins with hydrazine. Most of the compound showed potent cytotoxicity to MTT assay on five different human cancer cell lines.

B. ANTI-INFLAMMATORY ACTIVITY

- Druga Prasad *et. al* evaluated the anti-inflammatory activity of isatin derivatives by cotton pellet induced granuloma in Wistar rats. Microwave irradiation led to higher yields in less time than conventional methods.

- Ravi Jarapula *et.al* reported the synthesis and studied anti inflammatory activity of 2- hydroxy-N'– (2- oxoindolin-3-ylidene) benzohydrazide. The compounds were characterized and screened for *invivo* anti-inflammatory by carrageenan induced paw edema method.

C. ANTI LEISHMANIAL ACTIVITY

- Thiazolyl-isatin derivatives has been synthesized by Luiz Alberto Barros *et.al* and studied anti leishmanial activity. Chagas disease and leishmaniasis are considered as a threat to global health. Some of this thiazolyl-isatin was toxic for trypomastigotes without affecting macrophages viability. The potential cytotoxic profile of compounds was investigated by MTT assay using RAW 264.7 macrophage. Thiazolyl-isatin was evaluated *in vitro* against trypomastigote forms of *Trypanosoma cruzi*, Y strains.

- Novel coumarin – isatin hybrids were synthesized and their *in silico* and *invitro* anti leishmanial evaluations were performed. Molecular docking revealed the binding patterns of the synthesized compounds against the *L. tropica* drug target.

D. ANTI MICROBIAL ACTIVITY

- Krishna Srivastava *et.al* synthesized and characterized thiazole isatin hybrid and studied their antimicrobial activity. The presence of schiff bases and isatin enhances antimicrobial activity. All the synthesized compounds showed mild to moderate anti bacterial activity against tested bacteria.
- Sandra S Konstantinovic *et.al* synthesized isatin 3- thiosemicarbazone complexes with Co(II), Ni (II), Cu (II), Zn (II), Hg(II), and Pd(II). These were evaluated for antimicrobial activity and have enhanced action compared to ligand due to transition metal involved in coordination.
- P Sinduja *et.al* reported the reaction of mannich bases and isatin and evaluated their anti bacterial activity by cup plate method. The results were compared with standard ciprofloxacin.

E. ANTI TB ACTIVITY

- A novel class of triazole tethered coumarin isatin hybrids were developed and studied their anti mycobacterial evaluation was performed against *M. smegmatis* and MTB and their cytotoxicity in VERO cells.

F. ANTI HIV ACTIVITY

- Based on pharmacophore modeling, Tanushree *et al* synthesized various isatin thiosemicarbazide derivatives and evaluated their anti HIV activity. The synthesized compounds inhibited cytopathic effect of HIV 1. Compound 6 showed highest activity. All the synthesized compounds were found to be less active than the standard efavirenz.

- Vidhya S Pawar reported the molecular docking and designing of novel isatin analogs as efficient NNRTI for the treatment of AIDS. Docking results indicated that the compounds bind to NNRT binding site similar to the binding mode of inhibitors. ADME properties were also calculated.

G. LIPOXYGENASE ACTIVITY

- Tariq *et.als* synthesized series of isatin based thiazole derivatives, elucidated their structures with different spectroscopic techniques, such as FTIR and Proton nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy and screened for Lipoxygenase inhibitory potential.^[12]

H. . ANTICONVULSANT ACTIVITY

- Manjusha Verma et al reported the synthesis of Schiff bases of N methyl and N acetyl isatin derivatives and screened for their anticonvulsant activity against maximal electroshock (MES) and sub cutaneous metrazole (ScMet).^[18]

- Chinnasamy Rajaram Prakash synthesized series of novel Schiff bases of isatin and evaluated the anticonvulsant activity. The neurotoxicity of the compounds were also determined at the experimental dose levels.^[19]

I. ANTI DIABETIC ACTIVITY

- Fazal Rahim et. al synthesized and characterized the isatin based Schiff bases as α – glucosidase inhibitors. Only six analogs showed potent α glucosidase inhibitory potential with IC_{50} value ranging in between 2.2 ± 0.25 to $83.5 \pm 1.0 \mu\text{M}$ when compared with the standard acarbose.

- Ramandeep kaur et. al in 2019 designed, synthesized and characterized hybrids of isatin – pyrazole as potential α – glucosidase inhibitors. The tested compounds exhibited potent α glucosidase inhibition with IC_{50} values ranging from 3.26 ± 0.25 to $32.33 \pm 1.08 \mu\text{M}$. Docking studies further revealed that the compounds fitted well into the acarbose binding cavity of enzyme.

- Guangcheng wang *et.al* in 2017 synthesized novel chromone – isatin derivatives and studied their anti diabetic activity. The tested compounds exhibited excellent potent inhibitory activity in the range of IC_{50} 3.18 ± 0.12 to $16.59 \pm 0.17 \mu\text{M}$ as compared to the standard drug acarbose.

CONCLUSION:

The isatin can be found in a broad range of natural and synthetic compounds of medicinal importance. Isatin and its derivatives showed diverse pharmacological activities like anticonvulsant, anti-HIV, anticancer, antiviral, antibacterial, antifungal, anti-tubercular, antiglycation, anti-inflammatory, analgesic, antimalarial, antioxidant, anthelmintic and antianxiety activity.

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Declarations

a. Ethics approval and consent to participate

Not applicable

b. Consent for publication

I hereby consent for the publication of this article

c. Availability of data and materials

Not applicable

d. Competing interests

The author declare that there is no conflict of interest

e. Funding

Not applicable

f. Authors' contributions

MEGHANA.R contribution writing review and editing